

Workplace Spirituality Impact on Job Satisfaction: Mediating Role of Trust

Author's Details:

- ⁽¹⁾M.Adeel Abid, University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal
⁽²⁾Muhammad Mohsin, (Leading Author) University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal
⁽³⁾Summan Kokab, University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal
⁽⁴⁾Aqsa Parveen, University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal
⁽⁵⁾Zeshan Ali, University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal
⁽⁶⁾Naeem Shoukat, University of Gujrat, Sub-campus Narowal

Abstract:

Purpose – The basic aim of this research is to examine workplace spirituality impact and the trust factor on job satisfaction, among the banks in various cities of Punjab Pakistan

Design/methodology/approach – The data is collected to analyse the relationship between job satisfaction and workplace spirituality by asking questions directly to the employees of the banks. Trust among the organization and workplace is also tried to map on job satisfaction. Two hundred responses were taken under sample space belonging to various Banks, on the stratified basis, to show uniformity and impartiality of this research. Furthermore, the quantitative and statistical approach was used to examine the results and compile in a meaningful manner.

Findings- The finding of the study showed that workplace spirituality has a significant and positive relationship with job satisfaction and trust among the employees of organization and trust factor significantly mediates the relationship between workplace spirituality and the job satisfaction.

Research restraints- The study is limited to a number of banks in Pakistan only and employees are only manager operations, branch managers and relationship managers that were included in sample space. This can be increased to worldwide international banks and all the employees of the organization including accountants, cashiers, General Managers, Information Technology staffs, etc

Originality/value- The study shows that workplace spirituality increases the job satisfaction of the employees at the workplace.

Keywords: Workplace Spirituality, Trust, Job Satisfaction, Punjab banks.

1-Introduction:

The main objective of this paper is to show the workplace spirituality impact on job satisfaction by taking trust factor as a mediator. Employees are the biggest stakeholders of any organization that makes the organization successful. The success of any Bank is directly proportional to the loyalty of its employees towards their jobs. And the employees are only loyal to the organization if they are satisfied with their jobs. Job satisfaction has a strong relation with the spirituality of the workplace and the trust factor. If employees are satisfied with their jobs, they can add to the organization's performance. To provide state of the art facilities to the employees is the core responsibility of any organization that creates the relation of trust and this trust then form a bond between the organization and its employees that results in job satisfaction. If the bank is capable of performing its Corporate Social Responsibility, then the chances of job satisfaction increases.

Lack of spirituality in workplaces are causing many hurdles and disadvantages like absenteeism, negative organizational politics, and stress. In such cases, employees lose trust on each other and on the managerial staff of the organization, leading to the inefficient and unhealthy environment. This thing not only causes the limitation of organizational growth but the personal growth of employees as well. Only those peers perform extra ordinary during their working hours that feel a sense of connection and trust in the environment of the workplace. Showing directly that healthy and spiritual environment enhances the efficiency of the organization and the employees also feel performance measures and quantitative results satisfied. According to the perspective of the workplace spirituality, this research is conducted to analyse the impact of workplace spirituality. For this purpose, the study includes to analyse the impact on the employees of banks. The highly positive relationship of workplace spirituality on job satisfaction of Bank employees is found to exist. Previous research has only focused on data collection from executive members of the workplace, and just education sector was incorporated and taken into account. Since Education sector consists of highly educated and morally strong and satisfied people so that research was pretty predictable as it also showed a positive response on job satisfaction with respect to the spirituality of organization. But banking job is highly demanding and attention paying and any mistake in this sector can cause a loss of billions, so taking these people into our sample space for asking about job satisfaction was a tricky and courageous decision.

This study specifically puts emphasize on the selected banks of Punjab Pakistan, and further research can be conducted by adding branches of banks at national as well as international level. Selected ranks of employees and selected banks are impacting the results of our research. The organizational structure of this research is as follow: Previous work done on evaluating job satisfaction is explained in section-2. Determinants of job satisfaction and methodology are shown in Section-3. Section-4 explains the results and discussions. Section-5 presents the conclusion and recommends additions to this research for future upgradation.

2-Literature Review:

In this article portion, we reviewed different kinds of literature regarding workplace spirituality and its impact on job satisfaction and trust. The basic purpose of this portion is to check that how many studies on workplace spirituality and its impact on job satisfaction has already done in past years. Underlying literature shows different studies on workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, and trust.

Workplace spirituality impart a feeling of trust and interconnectivity between colleagues at the workplace, which provokes collegial feelings among employees and creates a healthy environment that is beneficial for the organizational culture, which is based upon motivation and enthusiasm. Such healthy practices not only flourish a positive corporate atmosphere but also enhance the overall efficiency of the organization in terms

of performance. As said by (Afsar and Rehman, 2015). Some people confuse workplace spirituality with religion, according to (Afsar and Rehman, 2015; Milliman et al., 2003), religion specifies the belief system and narrows the thinking of diversity and acceptance of freedom of expression and practice different faiths. Workplace spirituality opens minds for acceptance of tolerance from a different school of thoughts and interconnects different beliefs to integrate a concrete friendly environment, where there is no place for violence and sectarianism. Afsar and Rehman, (2015) are considered to be pioneers in the research related to workplace spirituality, and previously they had done great work explaining the relation of job satisfaction with community sense, moral values and meaningfulness of the work. We are now taking their research ahead because their research and results are verified and tested, so, we are broadening it to Banks and employees like Operational managers, relationship officers, and branch managers.

(Neck and Milliman, 1994) presented the importance of spirituality of workplace in a unique way, he said that opportunities for development and personal growth are more in organizations whose core values are to create a healthy spiritual environment at the workplace. They said, work itself is not important, but the attitude and behaviour of employees towards the work is a most important thing. The sense of personal growth will increase he enthusiasm and passion of employee, and that will increase the overall efficiency of the organization. Feelings of peers and knowledge increase when the workplace is spiritual, and a man feels like at home. If someone wants to add up in a meaningful way to the community, then he must work in a spiritual way that includes empathy, kindness, supporting others and being trustworthy. For integrating the peers and organizations, moral values should be used properly in work. For the development of interlinked actions and motivations, integration of horizontal and vertical spiritual dimensions and values are important (Giacalon and Jurkiewicz, 2003).

The individualistic culture was being preferred in the USA previously, but now-a-days spiritual values are considered important, and the trend is changing there too (Neck & Milliman, 1994). Companies and employee's performance will be enhanced by workplace spirituality. Life will be withered if work is without enthusiasm and passion. Three major reviews about spirituality are scared assessment, existential views and the most important, origin opinion (Krishnakumar & Neck, 2002). Enhanced trust, interconnectedness and motivational culture that leads the performance of any organization are all benefits of if workplace spirituality (Marques, 2005). Marques added that all this makes the organization successful and pushes it on the track of excellence. Many of the researchers consider workplace spirituality a positive impact on any organization, some of them have following views:

The perspective of individual spirit is foster and acknowledged by organizations (Thompson, 2000). Organizations are formed by individuals: thus, their individual spiritual needs must be addressed and taken into account (Thompson, 2000). Workplace spirituality contains three dimensions: community sense, work engagement, and connection of inner life. Workplace spirituality is the orientation of a person's inner self towards work and interconnection to community related to work environment spirituality (Kinjerski & Skrypnik, 2006; Luis Daniel, 2010).

Relation and interaction among employees and community have a strong bond, and that's called the sense of community and everyone has a strong bond of trust and dependence (Duchon & Plowman, 2005). Organizational values are affected by the abrupt changes in the environment, and every organization has set its own values and norms that are communicated towards employees, and everyone accepts it (Gupta, Kumar, & Singh, 2013). Milliman also insisted that organizational values are the most important factor for job satisfaction. An empirical study was carried

out on workplace spirituality and resulted that WPS plays an important role in peer's attitude (Giacalone and Jurkiewicz, 2003). Employee's inner self must be accomplished, and thus workplace spirituality and job satisfaction have a significant direct impact (Gupta et al., 2013). (Zare and Piryaee, 2013) said that, meaningful work has positive direct relation with job satisfaction. Job satisfaction also involves community sense. Job satisfaction is highly impacted by organizational values.

(Rahman, Daud, Chowdhury, Osmangani, & Hassan, 2015) all collectively agreed that people contain a part of emotional quality. Trust plays a major role to in generating cooperation between the employees of an organization. (Dirks & Ferrin, 2001).

(Ahmadi, Asgari and jamali, 2015) trustworthiness and mutual interconnectedness among peers consequently result in the excellence of an organization.

3-Data and Methodology:

In order to analyse the workplace spirituality and job satisfaction among different banks of Pakistan by mediating trust, the secondary data is gathered by filling the questionnaires from nearly 200 employees. Workplace Spirituality having Meaningful work, Sense of community and Organizational Values depicts the impact on Job satisfaction. Workplace Spirituality shows that job satisfaction can be boosted up by enlightening trust among the workers. Total of 24 questions was asked by each employee of banks that will be mapped to the job satisfaction and workplace spirituality.

3.1. Hypothesis

From the above framework, following hypotheses is anticipated:

H1: Workplace spirituality impacts positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

H2: Workplace spirituality impacts positively and significantly on trust between employees.

H3: Trust impacts positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

H4: Trust mediates the relationship between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction.

3.2. Research Methodology:

3.2.1. Sample selection

Using stratified sampling, the basic aim is to focus on the Banking sector to analyse the job satisfaction research.

3.2.2 Population frame

For collecting data, questionnaires were used, the target was to get 200 questionnaires solved by bank employees from which 150 questionnaires were received. Data analysing part will be started afterwards.

3.2.3. Unit of analysis

Employees like Banks managers, Manager Operations, and relationship officers were considered for filling the questionnaires.

3.2.4. Instrument development/selection

A quantitative method was used for data collection. Data was collected in the form of questionnaires from different banks. The scale of (Ayoko & Pekerti, 2008) was used in order to measure trust among employees and organization. This was based upon five-point marking scheme named Likert scale, where strongly agree carries 5 Marks and strongly disagree carries 1 mark. The questionnaire was used for calculating job satisfaction, and these questionnaires were adopted from already published research.

3.2.5. Proposed data collection procedures

The data will be obtained in the form of questionnaires, and these questionnaires are collected from the banking sector mostly from Punjab Pakistan. One hundred and fifty questionnaires were obtained in the form of hardcopy that the employees were asked to return after filling it.

3.2.6. Proposed data analysis techniques

Statistical analysis software SPSS was used for analysing data after collecting a sufficient number of responses from the employees. Correlation and regression will be used to interpret the results.

4-Empirical Results:

4.1. Correlation analysis

Correlation between a sense of community and meaningful work is .574 which shows a strong Relationship. Meaningful work and organization value = .279, which shows a weak association (Table 1). Inter correlation between meaningful value and trust = .57 and is another significant relation. It depicts that Job Satisfaction and trust = .518 which is significant as well.

Table 1: Correlation analysis (N=150)					
variable	MW	SOC	OV	Trust	JS
Meaningful Work	1				
Sense of Community	.574	1			
Organizational value	.474	.527	1		
Trust	.279	.024	.419	1	
Job Satisfaction	.436	.327	.844	.518	1

The basic purpose of this analysis was to considerate the relationship between workplace spirituality, trust and job satisfaction Table 2 embodies the relationship among all variables. There is a significant relation between workplace spirituality (i-e meaningful work, sense of community and organizational values) and job satisfaction. However, trust is non-significant with meaningful work and sense of community. On the other hand, there is a significant and positive relationship between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction by using trust as a mediator.

Table 2: Regression analysis Summary:

Hypothesized Results

Hypothesis Variables	β	Results
H1: Workplace Spirituality and Job Satisfaction	0.653	Significant
H2: Workplace Spirituality and Trust	0.28	Non-Significant
H3: Trust and Job Satisfaction	0.518	Significant
H4: Trust mediates the relationship	0.653	Significant
Between	0.354	
workplace spirituality and job satisfaction		

As mediator lessens the result of independent variable on dependent variable, so compact regression coefficient for workplace spirituality is accessible as 0.354

5-Discussion:

In our research, statistical technique that we used was linear regression to inspect the conjectured relationship between variables. Table II characterizes for checking the hypothesized relationship of the standardized statistical values of Beta. As in our proposed hypothesis, there is a positive relationship between workplace spirituality and job

satisfaction, and their statistical value is ($\beta = 0.653$) which shows H1 is significant. This hypothesis illustrates that in banks, workplace spirituality (meaningful work, sense of community and organizational values) would be in favour to increase the satisfaction level of job among employees. After the acceptance of first hypothesis, we will take second step in which workplace spirituality dimensions will be measured with trust which is a mediator but here trust will be treated as a dependent variable. A non-significant relationship between workplace spirituality and trust is established because the statistical value of Beta is ($\beta = 0.28$). Hence H2 is non-significant. This finding may enhance the understanding about the importance in determining the selection of dependent, independent and mediating variables to achieve the favourable results. In our third proposed hypothesis, trust has a positive relationship with job satisfaction and their statistical value is ($\beta = 0.518$). So H3 is significant. The last hypothesis, in which trust mediates the relationship between independent variable (workplace spirituality) and dependent variable (job satisfaction) will be measured to examine whether it reduces the effect of independent variable (workplace spirituality) on dependent variable (job satisfaction). If the effect of independent variable (workplace spirituality) on dependent variable (job satisfaction) is reduced in the presence of mediator (trust) then mediation appears. To test this condition, the present study scrutinises the change in regression value for workplace spirituality variable by entering the before and after values of trust variable. As regression coefficient of workplace spirituality and job satisfaction was ($\beta = 0.653$) and trust mediates the relationship between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction produced regression coefficient value for workplace spirituality is ($\beta = 0.354$), so in the factual sense, the effect of workplace spirituality on job satisfaction was reduced by ($0.653 - 0.354 = 0.299$) when trust treated as mediator. Accordingly, results shows that trust acts as a mediator between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction.

6-Conclusion:

After analysing and modelling the results, we came to the point that Workplace spirituality plays important role for job satisfaction of employees. Those employees who are provided with healthier environment and those who have sense of community, perform extraordinary as compared to others and develop a healthy environment for peers. Thus, they are satisfied with their jobs. The values of an organization play key role in defining the direction of the organization. If the values of organization are aiding spiritual environment, then the overall efficiency of the organization will improve because the individual employee will feel satisfied and will participate in uplifting and upgrading the existing model of governance for improving the interconnection and diversity of acceptance. Meaningful workplace will definitely help in improving the personal growth and peer to peer relationship, they will not take their job as a burden and it will enhance their skill set. Results also shows that trust acts as a mediator between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction. Hence, organizations must take into account the environment of workplace and spirituality for gaining trust of employees and providing them job satisfaction.

7-Recommendations:

The study is limited to a number of banks in Pakistan only and employees are only manager operations, managers and relationship managers that were included in sample space. This can be increased to worldwide international banks and all the employees of the organization including accountants, cashiers, General Managers, Information Technology staffs etc. Furthermore, this research is only limited to banks and it should also cover big organizations like universities, Software houses, Government secretariats and research centres.

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BIOGRAPHY

Mr. Muhammad Mohsin is a lecturer at the University of Gujrat, sub-campus Narowal. He can be contacted, Phone: 0092-303-3285583. Email: Muhammad.mohsin@uog.edu.pk

Mr. M. Adeel Abid is a lecturer at the University of Gujrat, sub-campus Narowal. He can be contacted, Phone: 0092-345-7454143.